

Dimension	Items	Scale	Source
Screening UK sample; 18 to 34 years old			
Participant identification	Please indicate your unique Prolific ID *Your individual participant identification ensures that your response can be deleted on request up to two weeks after taking part in the survey.	Open field	
Impulse buying frequency	How often do you make unplanned and spontaneous clothing purchases? If <i>Never</i> : Even though you have indicated that you never take part in unplanned and spontaneous clothing purchases, we would like you to imagine that you do in the following scenario.	1. Never 2. A few times a year 3. A few times a month 4. A few times per week 5. Every day	Adapted Moser (2020, p. 117)
Fleece purchase	I have bought a fleece top or I have considered buying a fleece top in the past. If <i>No</i> : Even though you have indicated that you have not bought or thought about buying a fleece top, we would like you to imagine that you did in the following scenario.	1. Yes 2. No	
Pre scenario	Do you purchase your own clothes more often online or in-store?	1. Online 2. In-store	
Tailored vignette: impulse purchase scenario	<i>(Online)</i> Imagine that you have a day off and want to use some of the time to get a new pair of trousers. You have opened the website of your favourite online shop and as you are browsing the pages, you notice a trendy and attractive fleece top . It is easy-going enough to be worn almost anywhere with anything. You like fleece because it is light, quick-drying and delivers all the warmth you need on a chill day at home, on a day out in the city or on hikes in the great outdoors. It happens to be in your size and favourite colour and you are already thinking about combining it with most of the clothes you own. It is on sale, today is the last day it is available online, and the shop is unlikely to get more tops like this in the future. Additionally, just today there is a special offer for a free and next-day delivery. <i>Note: You can proceed shortly.</i>		Partly based on Dholakia et al (2005, 2018)
	<i>(In-store)</i> Imagine that you have a day off and want to use some of the time to get a new pair of trousers. You have gone to your favourite shop in the city and as you are walking through the shop, you notice a trendy and attractive fleece top . It is easy-going enough to be worn anywhere with anything. You like fleece because it is light, quick-drying and delivers all the warmth you need on a chill day at home, on a day out in the city or on hikes in the great outdoors. It happens to be in your size and favourite colour. You try it on and feel instantly comfortable and confident wearing it with most of the clothes you own. It is on sale, and the piece on display is the last one left, and they are unlikely to get more tops like this in the future. <i>Note: You can proceed shortly.</i>		Partly based on Dholakia et al (2005, 2018)

Desire primer	Please take a few seconds to picture the top (e.g. colour, size, fit) and write down the most important reason of why you might want to buy it. Note: You can only write one reason.	Open field	
Desire primer check	Right now, how vividly do you picture the top?	0 Not at all, 10 Extremely	Adapted from May et al. (2014)
	Right now, how easy is it for you to imagine the top?	0 Not easy at all, 10 Extremely easy	
Reflection	<i>(Reflection A)</i> Please list three to five reasons for not buying the top. Start with the reasons which you feel are most important.	3-5 x Open field	Partly adapted from Moser (2020)
	<i>(Reflection B)</i> Please list three to five reasons for not buying the top Mention at least two reasons focusing on possible environmental impacts. Start with the reasons which you feel are most important.	3-5 x Open field	Partly adapted from Moser (2020); Based on Nielsen & Hofmann's findings (2021)
	<i>(Reflection C)</i> Now, please think about your favourite piece of clothing, one that you wear often. Describe in detail the happiest memory with that piece; when, for how long and why did you wear it.		Based on Dholakia et al. (2018)
Post reflection (dependent variables)	<i>Purchase Desire</i> Please indicate how strong your desire would be to buy the sweatshirt on a scale of 0 to 100 where 0 = no desire at all and 100 = very strong desire. My desire for buying the top can be described as:	0 No desire at all, 100 Very strong desire	Partly adapted from Dholakia et al. (2018)
	<i>Purchase Likelihood</i> Please indicate your likelihood of buying the top on a scale of 0 to 100 where 0 = definitely will not buy and 100 = definitely will buy. The likelihood that I would buy the top can be described as:	0 Definitely will not buy, 100 Definitely will buy	Adapted from Dholakia et al. (2005, 2018)
Impulse buying reduction	<i>Motivation</i> How motivated are you to reduce your amount of unplanned and spontaneous clothing purchases in the next month?	1 Completely unmotivated, 7 Completely motivated	Partly adapted from Moser (2020)
	<i>Self-efficacy</i> How confident are you to resist unplanned and spontaneous clothing purchases in the next month?	1 Completely unconfident, 7 Completely confident	Partly adapted from Moser (2020)
Intervention difficulty	<i>(Reflection A/B)</i> How difficult or easy was it for you to come up with reasons for not buying the top?	1 Very difficult, 4 Neither, 7 Very easy	Adapted from Moser (2020)

	<i>(Reflection C) How difficult or easy was it for you to come up with a clothing piece and describing your happiest memory of it in detail?</i>	1 Very difficult, 4 Neither, 7 Very easy	Partly adapted from Moser (2020)
Intervention experience	<i>(Reflection A/B)</i> Please describe what you liked, if anything, about coming up with reasons for not buying the top.	Open field (optional)	Adapted from Moser (2020)
	<i>(Reflection A/B)</i> Please describe what you disliked, if anything, about coming up with reasons for not buying the top.	Open field (optional)	Adapted from Moser (2020)
	<i>(Reflection A/B)</i> Below are some statements about the prior exercise of coming up with reasons not to buy the top. Please indicate how strongly you disagree (1) or agree (7). <i>IE1. During the exercise, I felt that my desire for the top became lower compared to before.</i> <i>IE2. The exercise was helpful in making a deliberative and reasonable consumer choice.</i> <i>IE3. I would like to try using the exercise when going shopping for clothes in the future.</i> <i>IE4. I am willing to recommend the exercise to people close to me who want to curb their clothes buying behaviour.</i>	1 Strongly disagree, 4 Neither, 7 Strongly agree	Adapted from Han et al. (2021)
	<i>(Reflection C)</i> Please describe what you liked, if anything, about describing your happiest memory with your favourite piece of clothing.	Open field (optional)	Adapted from Moser (2020)
	<i>(Reflection C)</i> Please describe what you disliked, if anything, about describing your happiest memory with your favourite piece of clothing.	Open field (optional)	Adapted from Moser (2020)
	<i>(Reflection C)</i> Below you can find statements about the prior exercise writing about your happiest memory with your favourite piece of clothing. Please indicate how strongly you disagree (1) or agree (7). <i>IE1. During the exercise, I felt that my desire for the product has become lower compared to before.</i> <i>IE2. The exercise was helpful in making a deliberative and reasonable consumer choice.</i> <i>IE3. I would like to try using the exercise when going shopping for clothes in the future.</i> <i>IE4. I am willing to recommend the exercise to people close to me who want to curb their clothing buying behaviour.</i>	1 Strongly disagree, 4 Neither, 7 Strongly agree	Adapted from Han et al. (2021)

Socio-demographics	We would like to ask you a few questions about yourself.	
Please indicate your age (in years)	List 18-34; Prefer not to answer; None of the above	
Please indicate your gender	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Female 2. Male 3. Non-binary 4. Other (open statement) 5. Prefer not to answer 	Nielsen & Hofmann (2021)
What is the highest level of education you completed?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No formal qualifications 2. Secondary School/ GCSE 3. College/ A levels 4. Undergraduate degree (NA/BSc/other) 5. Graduate degree (MA/MSc/MPhil/other) 6. Doctorate degree (PhD/MD/other) 7. Prefer not to answer 	Nielsen & Hofmann (2021)
What is your current employment status?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Employed (35 hours a week or more) 2. Employed (less than 35 hours a week) 3. Self-employed 4. Out of work and looking for work 5. Out of work but not currently looking for work 6. Homemaker 7. Student/in education 8. Military 9. Retired 10. Unable to work 11. Prefer not to answer 	Nielsen & Hofmann (2021)
Which of these descriptions comes closest to how you feel about your income?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Finding it very difficult on present income 2. Finding it difficult on present income 3. Coping on present income 4. Living comfortable with present income 5. Prefer not to answer 	Adapted from European Social Survey (2020)

Impulse buying tendency**Finally, please tell us a little about your personal approach when shopping for clothes.**

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| <i>IBT1.</i> When I go shopping for clothes, I buy clothing pieces that I had not intended to purchase. | 1 Strongly Disagree, 4 Neither, 7 Strongly Agree | Adapted from Weun et al. (1998); Moser (2020); Han et al. (2021) |
| <i>IBT2.</i> I am a person who makes unplanned clothing purchases. | | |
| <i>IBT3.</i> When I see a clothing item that really interests me, I buy it without considering the consequences. | | |
| <i>IBT4.</i> It is fun to buy clothes spontaneously. | | |
| <i>IBT5.</i> I avoid buying clothes that are not on my shopping list. (reverse) | | |

Note: Blue indicates item adaptations for this study. If no source is provided, we phrased the item.

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Information Sheet and Consent

Dear participant,

We would like to invite you to a study about young consumers' clothing purchase behaviour. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

What will the study involve?

You will read a description of a shopping scenario, followed by a small thought exercise and some questions about yourself and your purchase behaviour. The survey will take around 10 min to complete.

There are no risks when you participate in our study. You can terminate your participation in the study at any time without giving a reason and without any disadvantages. However, please note that you will not be compensated for your participation by Prolific in that case. The data and information collected in this survey will be kept strictly confidential. We will not ask you for your name in the study, but we ask for your Prolific ID in case you want to withdraw your data later. Your data will be held under the Austrian General Data Protection Regulation.

The anonymised dataset (without your Prolific ID) may later be uploaded onto a research cloud where it will be available freely for research purposes only. After the data has been analysed, a report of the findings will be submitted for publication. Only general trends will be reported and it will not be possible to identify individuals. A summary of the results is available from the researchers on request.

If you run into problems, have questions or decide that you would like your data to be deleted, please contact Maja Grünzner (maja.gruenzner@univie.ac.at). To withdraw your data, please write within two weeks after your participation and quote your Prolific ID; we will also ask you to enter this at the beginning of the study.

In case of any unresolved complaints, contact the data protection officer at the University of Vienna, Dr. Daniel Stanonik, LL.M. (dsba@univie.ac.at). Please save these details by noting them down or taking a screenshot.

Please read the statements below and tick the box at the bottom of the page to indicate your consent to take part.

I have received adequate information about the survey and about my rights as a participant.

I fully understand that my participation is voluntary, that the information I provide is confidential, and that I can withdraw at any point before submission of the survey and within two weeks after taking part by contacting the study lead.

Please select "I agree" to confirm that you want to take part in this study.

I agree

I do not agree

Debrief no consent

Thank you for considering a participation in our online survey.

We fully understand that you do not agree with the terms and that you have decided to not take part in our study.

As you do not wish to participate in this study, please close this survey and return your submission on Prolific by selecting the '**Stop without completing**' button.

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Debrief successful completion

Thank you for taking part in our study!

By taking part, you are helping to gather knowledge about young consumers shopping behaviour. This informs researchers developing interventions and communication strategies related to fashion consumption. If you have any questions about this study, please contact Maja Grünzner (maja.gruenzner@univie.ac.at). We would like to thank you again for your valuable contribution to this study. We greatly appreciate your participation.

On the following page, you will be redirected to let Prolific know that you successfully completed the study.

Best wishes,
Maja Grünzner

COMPLAINTS

If you are dissatisfied with the way the study is being conducted, please contact Maja Grünzner (maja.gruenzner@univie.ac.at) in the first instance.

If you feel that the problem has not been solved, please contact the data protection officer at the University of Vienna, Dr. Daniel Stanonik, LL.M. (dsba@univie.ac.at).

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